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Improving the stiffness of high resolution DLP stereolithographic material

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Background

- Photo-polymerization of liquid resin is a highly flexible additive manufacturing technique in that material properties can be modulated by adding other ingredients.
- By adding reinforcing agents, the mechanical properties of the resulting material can be enhanced.
- This work looks into the feasibility and effect of adding alumina particles and carbon nanotube into the resin to modify its modulus.
- The resin is cured layerwise and the effect of layer thickness on the Young's modulus will also be studied.

Materials and Methods

- Resin: Photomer 4012/Photomer 4017/Photomer 4028.
- Carbon nanotube (CNT) and alumina particles are used as reinforcing agents.
- ACER P1500 DLP projector with the lens inverted to project a full size image of $4.3 \times 2.42 \text{ mm}^2$, with a pixel resolution of $2.2 \mu\text{m}$.
- Cantilever beams with dimensions $60 \mu\text{m} \times 60 \mu\text{m} \times 600 \mu\text{m}$ on a $0.1 \times 0.1 \times 0.1 \text{ mm}$ base is printed on a cover slip with layer thickness of $2 \mu\text{m}$, $3 \mu\text{m}$ and $5 \mu\text{m}$.
- Tested using a FEMTO TOOLS miniature load cell and a Solartron Dfg1 LVDT.

Cantilever Specimens

Projected
image

Effect of reinforcement on Stiffness

Effect of curing layer thickness on Stiffness

Conclusions

- Adding reinforcing agents such as alumina particles or carbon nanotube can significantly increase the stiffness of DLP stereolithographic material.
- With a curing layer thickness of 5 μm , addition of 0.3wt% of CNT raised the Young's modulus by $\sim 47\%$ while addition of 1wt% of alumina particles increased it by 384%.
- Decreasing the curing layer thickness will also improve the Young's modulus. Without reinforcement, decreasing layer thickness from 5 to 2 μm raised modulus by 72%.
- With 0.3wt% of CNT, decreasing layer thickness from 5 to 2 μm raised modulus by 284%. With 1wt% of alumina, it increased by 340%.